

UNDERSTANDING THE PATTERN OF ONLINE CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR OF GEN Z - AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

Muddassir Khadar

Assistant Professor, MSNM Besant Institute of PG Studies, Mangalore

Email: muddassir.khadar@msnmbesant.edu.in /

ABSTRACT

Generation Z is slowly becoming a very large consumer segment, and it becomes even more imperative than ever to learn the methods of how to market to it. Understanding their online behavioural pattern while shopping will give us an insight into their buying behaviour. By 2020, Gen Z are expected to account for a nearly 40% of the entire consumer market. Generation Z is a digitally native generation meaning that they have been using technology right since they were born. They use social media to consume most of their information. This study aims to identify some of the behavioural patterns of Gen Z while shopping online and also tries to bring out some useful associations that will help marketers and others studying the behaviour of Gen Z. The results have shown that Gen Z prefer to do an extensive research before deciding to purchase online. They are more tuned to Instagram as the social media channel for getting information on deals. Their online spends are not connected to their household incomes and they are not influenced by celebrities.

Keywords: Gen Z, Online Shopping, Digital Natives, Influencer, Instagram

INTRODUCTION

Members of Gen Z are defined as people born from 1995 to 2010. Also known as Digital Natives. Right since childhood all throughout their youth, they have been exposed to the internet and to various social networks. For Gen Z, technology is something that is practically invisible; it's just a part and parcel of their world and the way they interact with it. Gen Z's most popular device is the smartphone. In a survey by IBM, 75% percent of them recorded that the mobile phone is the device they use the most and most of them are used to having a phone since they were 12 years old. Unsurprisingly, the Generation Z, has an even shorter attention span compared to millennial's. They are very impatient. Their inability to wait is so severe that Gen Z's attention span is estimated to be 8 seconds (Arthur Rachel,2016).55% of them are on their phones for more than 5 hours a day(Watson Heather,2019).This generation uses social media and search engines to find any information about the products that they'd like to purchase. They know how well to do their research, and pick up products based on their search of different resources.

OBJECTIVES & RELEVANCE OF STUDY

- To under the behavioural buying patterns of Gen Z while shopping online.
- To understand the association between checking user reviews for a product and comparing other websites.
- To understand the association between the household income and online spends.

Traditional marketing does not work for Gen Z. Digital Marketers need to embrace technology and unique ways of storytelling to cater to this crowd. There is a dire need to engage with and understand Gen Z who is turning out to be an increasingly significant group of customers that will help shape the future. As this population enters the workforce and their purchasing power increases, companies can no longer afford to use conventional methods. A much deeper knowledge of Gen Z customers is needed. This study tries to shed light on some of the behavioural patterns of Gen Z while shopping online and also tries to bring out some useful associations that will help marketers and others studying the behaviour of Gen Z. Ultimately the study will helps marketers to tailor their strategies for online shopping experience for the Gen Z population.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS

Online Usage: In the current world nearly 81% of Generation Z members regularly use social media and more than half of their purchase decisions are made online (Hulyk, 2015). These individuals spend their free time surfing the web, while at the same time chatting with friends, watching movies and doing their homework (McCrindle, 2019). Generation Z is the most informed and evolved generation. Hence, traditional marketing techniques that worked on previous generations are not relevant for Z members anymore. It is important to consider the behaviour and the perspective of Generation Z, as they have been identified as the next consumer powerhouse (Perlstein, 2017). Young people, who were born into this internet-enabled world, take full advantage of it. Simultaneous consumption of media content is typical of this generation (Palfrey and Gasser, 2008). The online shopping experience can further be improved if online vendors engage with buyers more through social media, blogs etc (Zhou et al., 2007).

Comparison to other Sites: Generation Z individuals visit social media websites, watch movies and serials, listen to music and shop online when surfing the web. While doing so, they encounter online advertisements which, if interesting, incline them to visit and explore websites. When they find products they like, they usually do not buy them immediately, but instead search for information on different websites about those products to find the best deals (Hidvégi, A.. Kelemen-Erdős A, 2016).

Influencer effect: Influencer marketing is being used by marketers as a tool to reach consumers, distributing information and influencing consumers product perceptions (Burke, 2017). Generation Z is on the top among the other generation who are interested in Social Media Influencers, nearly 84.5%, in the field of fashion and lifestyle (Adib Damara Satria, et al (2019). Gen Z look up to these Influencers or opinion leaders as role models and follow or mimic their behaviour in terms of what clothes they wear and which food do they consume etc.

Instagram Usage: For social media, members of Gen Z incline toward Instagram, Snapchat, and Youtube, according to a survey by Business Insider (Greenjul, Dennis, 2019). Gen Z prefer Snapchat and Instagram. Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn are less important (Kleinschmit, Matt, 2019).

Income and expenditure: 93% of parents say their children influence family spending and household purchases. Retailers, and in fact all businesses, hoping to connect to these savvy consumers and their immense purchasing power, need to understand who they are, what they want and how they want it (Marcie Merriman, 2015).

Impulsive behaviour: Gen Z are impatient and distracted having a short attention span. Information overload has left them with an attention span of just 8.25 seconds. With endless information at their fingertips, they are experts at swiftly assessing and filtering enormous amounts of content (Natalie Lambert, 2019).

Mode of Payment: As per the survey conducted by ACI Worldwide, Young consumers are willingly using e-wallet and UPI accounting for 42% for Gen Z & 48% for millennials (ETBFSI, 2019).

Hypothesis:

Ho: There is no significant association between checking User Reviews and Comparison of product to other websites.

Ho: There is no significant association between the household income and online spends

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study used both primary data and secondary sources which were collected from various journals, research papers, websites, various reports, books and articles published online. Primary Data was collected with a sample of 76 respondents within the age category of 19 to 24. The sample set of respondents were only from the non metro city of Mangalore. A well structured questionnaire was administered online via Google form survey. The responses were coded and entered in SPSS to generate different levels of output analysis in the form of tables and charts. Chi Square was used to measure Associations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Understanding the Respondents Profile:

Based on the demographic profile, the Gen Z sample (n = 76) had a mean age of 21.6 with 36.84% of males (28 make respondents) and 63.16% (48 female respondents) of females. The major age categories of respondents were 21 and 22 comprising of 38.16% and 23.68% of the total set of respondents respectively.

Table 1: Gender Wise Split of Respondents

		Gender			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	28	36.8	36.8	36.8
	Female	48	63.2	63.2	100.0
	Total	76	100.0	100.0	

Figure 1: Gender Wise Split of Respondents

Figure 2: Age Wise Split of Respondents

Understanding the Online Shopping Behavioural Patterns & Hypothesis Testing:

All the respondents chosen were from Mangalore Area. Majority (47.4%) reported to using the web for 3 to 4 hours per day with Sunday (78.9 %) being the most active day when they used the internet. Flipkart(72.4%) and Amazon(65.8%) were highly rated as the topmost used sites for shopping followed by Myntra(25%).

Testing Ho: There is no significant association between checking User Reviews and Comparison of product to other websites. Performing a Chi Square test to test the association between these two variables, we get -

Table 2: Chi Square Test

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.554 ^a	4	.235
Likelihood Ratio	5.412	4	.248
Linear-by-Linear Association	.516	1	.472
N of Valid Cases	76		

The value of .235 is greater than 0.05 (5% level of confidence). The result is statistically insignificant and we accept reject the Null hypothesis. Thus there is no significant association between checking User Reviews and Comparison of product to other websites. So it is not necessary that if someone checks for User Reviews, he would also cross check other websites for the same info.

Understanding the influencer effect on Gen Z, we can see from below table that a cumulative 89.5% either disagree or “neutral” from which we can conclude that influencers or celebrities do not make an impact on the Gen Z populace.

Table 3: Influencer Stats

		Influencer			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	10.5	10.5	10.5
	Disagree	27	35.5	35.5	46.1
	Neutral	33	43.4	43.4	89.5
	Agree	7	9.2	9.2	98.7
	Strongly Agree	1	1.3	1.3	100.0
	Total	76	100.0	100.0	

As Greenjul and Kleinschmit have pointed out in their previous research, the current study confirms that Gen Z are more inclined towards Instagram as a means of getting the information about advertisement on products and deals (Figure 3a). It also revealed that social media(67.1%) is the source through which the Gen Z get to know about the promo deals and Instagram being the major source. An interesting data about respondents reveals only 9% reference the newspaper print ad which shows the declining usage of print media over online media.

Figure 3: Ad Channel for advertisements

Figure 3a: Specific social media channel for advertisements

Figure 4: Figure showing Eagerness of Gen Z

Figure 5: Mode of Payment

As reported by Natalie Lambert, even though Gen Z have a short attention span of just 8.25 seconds and are very impatient, the study finds that nearly 80% are ready to wait for discounts and festival sales before deciding to make a purchase online (Figure 4). Also as reported by ETBFSI, 42% of Gen Z prefer Wallet payments, the current study highlights the usage of Cash on Delivery (63.2%) as the major mode of preferred payment followed by Wallet payments (13.2%) - Refer Figure 5.

Testing Ho: There is no significant association between the household income and online spends.

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.119 ^a	12	.519
Likelihood Ratio	10.766	12	.549
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.637	1	.104
N of Valid Cases	76		

The value of .519 is greater than 0.05 (5% level of confidence). The result is statistically insignificant and we would accept the Null hypothesis. Thus there is no significant association between the household incomes of Gen Z and their online spends.

As reported by Adib Damara Satria, Gen Z majorly prefers fashion and Lifestyle products. The current study also reiterates the same as major portion of the respondents (75%) reported shopping for Fashion items online.

Figure 6: Items shopped Online.

CONCLUSION

Gen Z are estimated to be between 2 and 2.52 billion. Also called Digital natives, they socialize and learn to live in a digital world of their own. Shorter attention spans, heavy media consumption and extensive research information at their fingertips allows Gen Z to make more informed decisions. Based on the findings of the research study on the Hypothesis, there is no connection between the household income and online spends. Most of the category of spenders lies in the range of below 1000. Furthermore,

there is also no connection between checking the User ratings for a product and searching for further information on other shopping websites. Instagram turned out to be the most popular used social media channel as also reported in numerous studies prior to this study. Gen Z wait for discounts and other sales before making a purchase and are not so much influenced by celebrities. They learn to make their own choices based on information research. Gen Z is mostly online for nearly 3 to 4 hours per day having a peak usage on Sunday. Flipkart and Amazon turned out to be the most widely used online media channel for shopping preferring the mode of payment as cash followed by wallet payments. Bank tieups and offering heavy Discounts on Wallet payments can push the Youngsters towards to go more Digital. Among the items consumed, shopping for fashion and beauty products ranked the highest whether it was male or female category. It is really important for brands to adopt their marketing strategies by making social media an essential part of their business in order to meet the expectations of the latest generation of consumers.

REFERENCES

- Adib Damara Satria, Sarah Jatipuri, Anggia Desvhi Hartanti, Lim Sanny (2019). The Impact of Celebrity Endorsement by Social Influencer Celebgram on Purchase Intention of Generation Z in Fashion Industry. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)*. ISSN: 2277-3878, Volume-8 Issue-2S.
- Burke, K.E., 2017. Social Butterflies-How Social Media Influencers are the New Celebrity Endorsement (Doctoral dissertation, Virginia Tech).
- ETBFSI (2019). *Consumers opt for digital payments over cash in festive season*. Available at: <https://bfsi.economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/fintech/consumers-opt-for-digital-payments-over-cash-in-festive-season/71714794>
- Greenjul, Dennis (2019). *The Most Popular Social Media Platforms With Gen Z*. Available: <https://www.businessinsider.in/retail/the-most-popular-social-media-platforms-with-gen-z/articleshows/70044989.cms>. Accessed on: November 5 2019.
- Hulyk, T.(2015). Marketing to Gen Z: uncovering a new world of social media influencers. Available at: <https://www.franchise.org/marketing-to-gen-z-uncovering-a-new-world-of-social-media-influencers>. Accessed on: 20 November 2019.
- Watson, Heather(2019.) *How Obsessed Is Gen Z With Mobile Technology?* Available at: <https://genhq.com/how-obsessed-is-gen-z-with-mobile-technology/>. Accessed on: November 15 2019
- Hidvégi, A., Kelemen- Erdős A. (2016): Assessing the Online Purchasing Decisions of Generation Z. In Reicher R. Zs. (ed.) (2016): Proceedings of FIKUSZ 2016, Óbuda University, Budapest, Hungary, pp. 173-181.
- Kleinschmit, Matt(2019). *Generation Z Characteristics: 5 Infographics on the Gen Z Lifestyle*. Available at: <https://www.visioncritical.com/blog/generation-z-infographics>. Accessed on: November 7 2019
- McCrindle (2010). *Generation Z defined: global, visual, digital*. Available at: http://mccrindle.com.au/the-mccrindle-blog/generation_z_defined_global_visual_digital. Accessed: 26 November 2019.
- Marcie Merriman (2015). EY-rise-of-gen-znew-challenge-for-retailers. *Ernst & Young LP*. Available at: <https://www.ey.com/Publication/vwLUAssets/EY-rise-of-gen-znew-challenge-for-retailers/%24FILE/EY-rise-of-gen-znew-challenge-for-retailers.pdf>
- Natalie Lambert (2019). *An (in)convenient truth: Gen Z and the culture of instant gratification*. Available at: <https://www.sapho.com/blog/an-inconvenient-truth-gen-z-and-the-culture-of-instant-gratification/>
- Palfrey, J., Gasser, U.: *Born Digital*. Basic Books, New York, 2008
- Perlstein, J (2017). Engaging Generation Z: marketing to a new brand of consumers. WWW document. Available at: <http://www.adweek.com/digital/josh-perlstein-response-media-guest-post-generation-z/>. Accessed on: December 5 2019.
- Arthur, Rachel (2016). *Generation Z: 10 Stats From SXSW You Need To Know*. Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/rachelarthur/2016/03/16/generation-z/#7231258e2909>. Accessed on: November 15 2019
- Zhou, L., Dai, L., & Zhang, D. (2007). Online shopping acceptance model: A critical survey of consumer factors in online shopping. *Journal of Electronic Commerce Research*, 8 (1), 41-62.